

Supplementary Materials for Improved Community Detection using Stochastic Block Models

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Contents

A	List of Datasets	3
B	Additional Tables	4
C	Additional Figures	9
D	Description Length	13
E	Commands and Versions	16

List of Figures

S1	Impact of Treatment on NMI scores of Selected SBM (heatmap)	9
S2	Impact of Treatment on AMI scores of Selected SBM (heatmap)	10
S3	Models selected by SBM on LFR networks	11
S4	Impact of Treatment on ARI scores of Selected SBM (bar chart)	12
S5	SBM to SBM-CC ratios for DL components that favor SBM	14
S6	SBM-CC to SBM ratios for DL components that favor SBM-CC	15

List of Tables

S1	Impact of Selected SBM and treatments on Average Cluster Size per Empirical Dataset Group	4
S2	Impact of Selected SBM and treatments on Min/Median/Max Cluster Size per Empirical Dataset Group	4
S3	Impact of Selected SBM and treatments on Average Number of Clusters per Empirical Dataset Group	5
S4	NMI/ARI accuracy of clustering methods on synthetic CPM (r=0.0001) LFR networks	5
S5	NMI/ARI accuracy of clustering methods on synthetic CPM (r=0.001) LFR networks	6
S6	NMI/ARI accuracy of clustering methods on synthetic CPM (r=0.01) LFR networks	6
S7	NMI/ARI accuracy of clustering methods on synthetic CPM (r=0.1) LFR networks	7
S8	NMI/ARI accuracy of clustering methods on synthetic CPM (r=0.5) LFR networks	7
S9	NMI/ARI accuracy of clustering methods on synthetic Modularity LFR networks	8

A List of Datasets

Small datasets (10) from the Peixoto Collection Sorted by Increasing Node Count sa_companies; november17; dutch_criticism; ceo_club; elite; macaque_neural; sp_kenyan_households; contiguous_usa; cs_department; dolphins

Medium-size datasets (103) from the Peixoto Collection Sorted by Increasing Node Count dnc; uni_email; polblogs; faa_routes; netscience; new_zealand_collab; collins_yeast; interactome_stelzl; bible_nouns; plant_pol_robertson; at_migrations; interactome_figeys; us_air_traffic; drosophila_flybi; fly_larva; interactome_vidal; openflights; bitcoin_alpha; fediverse; power; advogato; bitcoin_trust; jung; reactome; jdk; elec; chess; sp_infectious; wiki_rfa; dblp_cite; anybeat; chicago_road; foldoc; inploid; google; escorts; marvel_universe; fly_hemibrain; internet_as; word_assoc; cora; movielens_100k; lkml_reply; nematode_mammal; linux; topology; email_enron; pgp_strong; paris_transportation; facebook_wall; slashdot_threads; python_dependency; marker_cafe; jester; epinions_trust; slashdot_zoo; twitter_15m; prosper; wiki_link_dyn; livemocha; wikiconflict; dbpedia_writer; lastfm_aminer; wiki_users; digg_votes; wordnet; dbtropes_feature; douban; dbpedia_starring; github; dbpedia_recordlabel; dbpedia_producer; academia_edu; google_plus; libimseti; dbpedia_location; dbpedia_occupation; email_eu; dbpedia_genre; discogs_label; wiki_article_words; stanford_web; dblp_coauthor_snap; notre_dame_web; corporate_directors; lkml_thread; citeseer; bookcrossing; twitter; flickr_groups; visualizeus; dbpedia_country; petster; stackoverflow; yahoo_ads; berkstan_web; eu_procurements; myspace_aminer; google_web; epinions; citeulike; dbpedia_team; bibsonomy

Large datasets (7) from the Peixoto Collection Sorted by Increasing Node Count reuters; hyves; discogs_affiliation; amazon_ratings; livejournal; bitcoin; dblp_author_paper

Other datasets (2) orkut; CEN (Curated Exosome Network)

B Additional Tables

Table S1: **Impact of Selected SBM and treatments on Average Cluster Size per Empirical Dataset Group** For each real-world dataset group by size, the average cluster size for all non-singleton clusters is shown. We show this for the selected SBM model and its follow-up treatments for each model. Note that the selected SBM model is different per dataset as it is selected by running all degree corrected, non degree corrected, and planted partition SBM models and selecting the model that yielded the lowest description length. On one of the large datasets, WCC ran into a memory error with 256GB of RAM, hence the results for dataset is omitted in this table.

	small	medium	large
Selected SBM	17.65	3905.52	24927.68
Selected SBM - CC	17.65	20.87	61.60
Selected SBM - WCC	15.90	9.89	27.13
Selected SBM - CM	15.90	20.17	27.61

Table S2: **Impact of Selected SBM and treatments on Min/Median/Max Cluster Size per Empirical Dataset Group** For each real-world dataset group by size, the minimum/median/maximum cluster sizes for all non-singleton clusters is shown. We show this for the selected SBM model and its follow-up treatments for each model. Note that the selected SBM model is different per dataset as it is selected by running all degree corrected, non degree corrected, and planted partition SBM models and selecting the model that yielded the lowest description length. On one of the large datasets, WCC ran into a memory error with 256GB of RAM, hence the results for dataset is omitted in this table.

	small	medium	large
Selected SBM	16.40/17.65/18.90	534.03/1523.88/33856.57	317.33/12304.67/211757.44
Selected SBM - CC	16.40/17.65/18.90	1.99/7.35/2554.30	1.78/2.89/40937.22
Selected SBM - WCC	14.70/15.90/17.10	1.87/4.65/288.69	1.75/2.12/1448.00
Selected SBM - CM	14.70/15.90/17.10	2.13/16.80/227.74	1.78/5.89/1115.56

Table S3: **Impact of Selected SBM and treatments on Average Number of Clusters per Empirical Dataset Group** For each real-world dataset group by size, the average number of clusters for all non-singleton clusters is shown. We show this for the selected SBM model and its follow-up treatments for each model. Note that the selected SBM model is different per dataset as it is selected by running all degree corrected, non degree corrected, and planted partition SBM models and selecting the model that yielded the lowest description length. On one of the large datasets, WCC ran into a memory error with 256GB of RAM, hence the results for dataset is omitted in this table.

	small	medium	large
Selected SBM	1.10	324.09	3305.00
Selected SBM - CC	1.10	3370.95	75939.22
Selected SBM - WCC	1.10	4074.93	83927.88
Selected SBM - CM	1.10	1732.83	28127.44

Table S4: **NMI/ARI accuracy of clustering methods on synthetic CPM ($r=0.0001$) LFR networks** The NMI/ARI accuracies for each of the methods and their treatments using WCC, CC, or CM are shown. Bold text indicates the selected SBM model with the lowest description length for each dataset.

	cit_hepph	cit_patents	wiki_topcats	cen	oc
Leiden-Mod	0.91/0.82	0.67/0.01	0.91/0.74	0.76/0.06	0.69/0.01
Leiden-Mod - WCC	0.95/0.90	0.98/0.88	0.95/0.82	0.95/0.40	0.88/0.01
Leiden-Mod - CC	0.91/0.82	0.67/0.01	0.91/0.74	0.76/0.06	0.69/0.01
Leiden-Mod - CM	0.97/0.93	0.98/0.83	0.93/0.43	0.96/0.88	0.99/0.90
Leiden-CPM(0.001)	0.95/0.90	0.95/0.73	0.99/1.00	0.97/0.95	0.96/0.56
Leiden-CPM(0.001) - WCC	0.96/0.92	1.00/0.98	1.00/1.00	1.00/0.99	0.98/0.64
Leiden-CPM(0.001) - CC	0.95/0.90	0.95/0.73	0.99/1.00	0.97/0.95	0.96/0.56
Leiden-CPM(0.001) - CM	0.96/0.92	1.00/0.98	1.00/1.00	1.00/0.99	0.98/0.64
DC SBM	0.93/0.87	0.78/0.06	0.96/0.94	0.85/0.25	0.85/0.10
non DC SBM	0.92/0.55	0.78/0.06	0.93/0.67	0.84/0.21	0.86/0.10
PP SBM	0.95/0.33	0.97/0.60	0.94/0.89	0.91/0.58	0.96/0.56
Selected SBM	0.95/0.33	0.97/0.60	0.96/0.94	0.91/0.58	0.96/0.56
Selected SBM - WCC	0.95/0.34	1.00/0.69	1.00/1.00	1.00/0.99	1.00/0.94
Selected SBM - CC	0.95/0.33	0.97/0.60	0.98/0.97	0.94/0.73	0.96/0.56
Selected SBM - CM	0.95/0.33	0.99/0.68	0.83/0.36	0.97/0.73	0.99/0.90

Table S5: **NMI/ARI accuracy of clustering methods on synthetic CPM ($r=0.001$) LFR networks**
The NMI/ARI accuracies for each of the methods and their treatments using WCC, CC, or CM are shown.
Bold text indicates the selected SBM model with the lowest description length for each dataset.

	cit_hepph	cit_patents	wiki_topcats	cen	oc
Leiden-Mod	0.98/1.00	0.68/0.00	0.83/0.40	0.69/0.02	0.67/0.01
Leiden-Mod - WCC	0.99/1.00	0.98/0.81	0.90/0.52	0.91/0.23	0.69/0.01
Leiden-Mod - CC	0.98/1.00	0.68/0.00	0.83/0.40	0.69/0.02	0.67/0.01
Leiden-Mod - CM	0.99/1.00	0.96/0.66	0.98/0.88	0.93/0.62	0.97/0.42
Leiden-CPM(0.001)	0.99/1.00	0.96/0.55	0.98/0.96	0.96/0.88	0.96/0.40
Leiden-CPM(0.001) - WCC	1.00/1.00	1.00/0.95	0.99/0.96	0.99/0.96	0.97/0.43
Leiden-CPM(0.001) - CC	0.99/1.00	0.96/0.55	0.98/0.96	0.96/0.88	0.96/0.40
Leiden-CPM(0.001) - CM	1.00/1.00	1.00/0.95	0.99/0.96	0.99/0.96	0.97/0.43
DC SBM	0.99/1.00	0.79/0.03	0.92/0.83	0.83/0.18	0.86/0.11
non DC SBM	0.95/0.85	0.79/0.03	0.83/0.09	0.81/0.12	0.86/0.11
PP SBM	0.86/0.51	0.99/0.89	0.88/0.67	0.89/0.40	0.97/0.70
Selected SBM	0.99/1.00	0.99/0.89	0.92/0.83	0.89/0.40	0.97/0.70
Selected SBM - WCC	1.00/1.00	1.00/0.99	1.00/0.99	0.99/0.88	1.00/0.95
Selected SBM - CC	0.99/1.00	0.99/0.89	0.98/0.95	0.94/0.61	0.97/0.70
Selected SBM - CM	1.00/1.00	1.00/0.99	0.85/0.26	0.96/0.51	0.99/0.94

Table S6: **NMI/ARI accuracy of clustering methods on synthetic CPM ($r=0.01$) LFR networks**
The NMI/ARI accuracies for each of the methods and their treatments using WCC, CC, or CM are shown.
Bold text indicates the selected SBM model with the lowest description length for each dataset.

	cit_hepph	cit_patents	wiki_topcats	cen	oc
Leiden-Mod	0.88/0.66	0.65/0.01	0.65/0.02	0.49/0.00	0.64/0.01
Leiden-CPM(0.001) - WCC	0.92/0.83	1.00/0.98	0.98/0.90	0.99/0.62	0.97/0.55
Leiden-Mod - CC	0.88/0.66	0.65/0.01	0.65/0.02	0.49/0.00	0.64/0.01
Leiden-Mod - CM	0.90/0.69	0.94/0.47	0.95/0.78	0.88/0.01	0.65/0.01
Leiden-CPM(0.001)	0.92/0.82	0.95/0.78	0.95/0.87	0.96/0.52	0.97/0.53
Leiden-CPM(0.001) - WCC	0.92/0.83	1.00/0.98	0.98/0.90	0.99/0.62	0.97/0.55
Leiden-CPM(0.001) - CC	0.92/0.82	0.95/0.78	0.95/0.87	0.96/0.52	0.97/0.53
Leiden-CPM(0.001) - CM	0.92/0.83	1.00/0.98	0.98/0.90	0.99/0.62	0.97/0.55
DC SBM	0.93/0.88	0.79/0.07	0.84/0.22	0.82/0.07	0.88/0.17
non DC SBM	0.92/0.70	0.79/0.07	0.81/0.13	0.74/0.02	0.88/0.16
PP SBM	0.90/0.68	0.95/0.62	0.85/0.23	0.97/0.71	0.99/0.89
Selected SBM	0.93/0.88	0.95/0.62	0.85/0.23	0.97/0.71	0.99/0.89
Selected SBM - WCC	0.99/0.98	1.00/0.83	0.99/0.67	0.99/0.95	1.00/0.97
Selected SBM - CC	0.95/0.91	0.95/0.63	0.93/0.47	0.97/0.73	0.99/0.89
Selected SBM - CM	0.99/0.99	0.99/0.65	0.96/0.35	0.99/0.93	1.00/0.97

Table S7: **NMI/ARI accuracy of clustering methods on synthetic CPM (r=0.1) LFR networks**
The NMI/ARI accuracies for each of the methods and their treatments using WCC, CC, or CM are shown. cen is omitted in this table due to ground truth clusters for cen under 0.1 setting being highly disconnected. Bold text indicates the selected SBM model with the lowest description length for each dataset.

	cit_hepph	cit_patents	wiki_topcats	oc
Leiden-Mod	0.98/0.90	0.49/0.00	0.34/0.00	0.60/0.00
Leiden-Mod - WCC	0.98/0.90	0.92/0.13	0.85/0.00	0.60/0.00
Leiden-Mod - CC	0.98/0.90	0.49/0.00	0.34/0.00	0.60/0.00
Leiden-Mod - CM	0.98/0.90	0.92/0.11	0.88/0.00	0.60/0.00
Leiden-CPM(0.001)	1.00/1.00	0.94/0.39	0.90/0.05	0.98/0.73
Leiden-CPM(0.001) - WCC	1.00/1.00	0.99/0.82	0.94/0.05	0.98/0.74
Leiden-CPM(0.001) - CC	1.00/1.00	0.94/0.39	0.90/0.05	0.98/0.73
Leiden-CPM(0.001) - CM	1.00/1.00	0.99/0.82	0.94/0.05	0.98/0.74
DC SBM	1.00/1.00	0.77/0.02	0.76/0.02	0.90/0.25
non DC SBM	0.97/0.71	0.77/0.02	0.60/0.00	0.87/0.16
PP SBM	1.00/1.00	0.96/0.59	0.86/0.12	1.00/0.98
Selected SBM	1.00/1.00	0.96/0.59	0.86/0.12	1.00/0.98
Selected SBM - WCC	1.00/1.00	1.00/0.99	0.99/0.82	1.00/0.98
Selected SBM - CC	1.00/1.00	0.96/0.59	0.91/0.24	1.00/0.98
Selected SBM - CM	1.00/1.00	1.00/0.98	0.96/0.65	1.00/0.98

Table S8: **NMI/ARI accuracy of clustering methods on synthetic CPM (r=0.5) LFR networks**
The NMI/ARI accuracies for each of the methods and their treatments using WCC, CC, or CM are shown. wiki_topcats and cen are omitted in this table due to LFR failing on wiki_topcats under 0.5 setting and ground truth clusters for cen under 0.5 setting being highly disconnected. Bold text indicates the selected SBM model with the lowest description length for each dataset. Time out indicates that the corresponding method or treatment did not complete after 72 hours.

	cit_hepph	cit_patents	oc
Leiden-Mod	0.28/0.02	0.24/0.00	0.29/0.00
Leiden-Mod - WCC	0.38/0.03	0.95/0.02	time out
Leiden-Mod - CC	0.28/0.02	0.24/0.00	0.29/0.00
Leiden-Mod - CM	0.38/0.03	0.95/0.01	0.79/0.00
Leiden-CPM(0.001)	0.24/0.02	0.82/0.03	0.97/0.71
Leiden-CPM(0.001) - WCC	0.51/0.02	0.94/0.13	0.97/0.75
Leiden-CPM(0.001) - CC	0.24/0.02	0.82/0.03	0.97/0.71
Leiden-CPM(0.001) - CM	0.51/0.02	0.94/0.13	0.97/0.75
DC SBM	0.00/0.00	0.00/0.00	0.01/0.00
non DC SBM	0.01/0.00	0.01/0.00	0.01/0.00
PP SBM	0.00/0.00	0.00/0.00	0.80/0.15
Selected SBM	0.00/0.00	0.00/0.00	0.80/0.15
Selected SBM - WCC	0.00/0.00	time out	0.95/0.75
Selected SBM - CC	0.00/0.00	0.00/0.00	0.85/0.25
Selected SBM - CM	0.00/0.00	0.95/0.00	0.92/0.57

Table S9: **NMI/ARI accuracy of clustering methods on synthetic Modularity LFR networks**
The NMI/ARI accuracies for each of the methods and their treatments using WCC, CC, or CM are shown.
Bold text indicates the selected SBM model with the lowest description length for each dataset.

	cit_hepph	cit_patents	wiki_topcats	cen	oc
Leiden-Mod	0.99/1.00	0.77/0.14	0.83/0.10	0.90/0.41	0.84/0.15
Leiden-Mod - WCC	1.00/1.00	1.00/1.00	0.91/0.21	0.97/0.68	0.98/0.58
Leiden-Mod - CC	0.99/1.00	0.77/0.14	0.83/0.10	0.90/0.41	0.84/0.15
Leiden-Mod - CM	0.99/1.00	0.99/0.99	1.00/0.93	0.99/0.96	1.00/0.99
Leiden-CPM(0.001)	1.00/1.00	0.97/0.92	1.00/0.96	1.00/1.00	0.99/0.95
Leiden-CPM(0.001) - WCC	1.00/1.00	1.00/0.94	1.00/0.96	1.00/1.00	1.00/1.00
Leiden-CPM(0.001) - CC	1.00/1.00	0.97/0.92	1.00/0.96	1.00/1.00	0.99/0.95
Leiden-CPM(0.001) - CM	1.00/1.00	1.00/0.94	1.00/0.96	1.00/1.00	1.00/1.00
DC SBM	1.00/1.00	0.82/0.29	0.89/0.24	0.94/0.67	0.89/0.30
non DC SBM	0.95/0.87	0.82/0.30	0.88/0.21	0.93/0.62	0.89/0.27
PP SBM	0.96/0.96	0.95/0.50	0.99/0.89	0.98/0.96	0.94/0.62
Selected SBM	1.00/1.00	0.95/0.50	0.99/0.89	0.98/0.96	0.94/0.62
Selected SBM - WCC	1.00/1.00	0.99/0.54	1.00/0.95	1.00/1.00	1.00/0.98
Selected SBM - CC	1.00/1.00	0.96/0.52	0.99/0.90	0.99/0.98	0.97/0.83
Selected SBM - CM	1.00/1.00	0.97/0.38	1.00/0.95	0.94/0.70	0.98/0.94

C Additional Figures

Figure S1: **Impact of Treatment on NMI Scores of Selected SBM (heatmap)**. Blue colors indicate that post-processing using the corresponding treatment improves NMI accuracy for the clustering method, and orange and red colors indicate that treatment hurts NMI accuracy, and yellow indicates neutral impact. All treatments are done without filtering for size. n.a. indicates that a network was either not used because of too many disconnected ground-truth clusters or that the LFR software failed to generate the network. t.o. indicates that WCC on the 0.5 cit_patents timed out after 72 hours.

Figure S2: **Impact of Treatment on AMI Scores of Selected SBM (heatmap)**. Blue colors indicate that post-processing using the corresponding treatment improves AMI accuracy for the clustering method, and orange and red colors indicate that treatment hurts AMI accuracy, and yellow indicates neutral impact. All treatments are done without filtering for size. n.a. indicates that a network was either not used because of too many disconnected ground-truth clusters or that the LFR software failed to generate the network. t.o. indicates that WCC on the 0.5 cit_patents timed out after 72 hours.

Figure S3: **Lowest Description Length Model for LFR** The selected model (based on minimizing the description length) among degree-corrected, non degree-corrected, and Planted Partition SBM is shown for each of the LFR dataset settings. n.a. indicates that a network was either not used because of too many disconnected ground-truth clusters or that the LFR software failed to generate the network.

Figure S4: **Impact of Treatment on ARI Scores of Selected SBM (bar chart)**. n.a. indicates that a network was either not used because of too many disconnected ground-truth clusters or that the LFR software failed to generate the network. t.o. indicates that WCC on the 0.5 cit_patents timed out after 72 hours.

D Description Length

In this section, we provide a brief explanation for description length favoring untreated SBM clusterings over SBM-CC clusterings. Our goal is to illustrate one possible reason why degree-corrected SBM alone (without the CC treatment) favors a smaller number of potentially disconnected clusters rather than breaking them up into more clusters, all being connected.

Description length The description length of an adjacency matrix A and a clustering b under the degree corrected SBM model is

$$DL(A, b) = -\log p(A, b, e, k) \tag{1}$$

$$= -\log p(A|b, e, k) - \log p(k|b, e) - \log p(b) - \log p(e) \tag{2}$$

where k is the degree vector (induced by A) and e is the edge count matrix (induced by A and b).

From Eq 2, the description length can be decomposed into four parts, which are the negative logarithms of the model likelihood ($-\log p(A|b, e, k)$), the prior for the degree ($-\log p(k|b, e)$), the prior for the block assignment ($-\log p(b)$), and the prior for the edge count matrix ($-\log p(e)$). `graph-tools` provides the functionality for computing these quantities separately, which we will use for the following analysis.

Breakdown of the description length In the main text, we showed the breakdown of the description length into these components for an example network (`linux`). Similarly, we compute the components of the description length for all networks that select the SBM(DC) model, with and without the CC treatment. There are 103 such networks.

Figure S5 illustrates the ratio, for those components in the description length that favor SBM, of the score of SBM to the score of SBM-CC, while Figure S6 shows the inverse of that ratio for the components that favor SBM-CC. Thus, all ratios shown in these figures are between 0 and 1, and the closer to 0, the more heavily the clustering is favored (since smaller description lengths are desired). This means that for $DL(A, b)$, $-\log p(e)$, and $-\log p(b)$, the value is higher with the SBM-CC for all networks we considered here. Similarly, for $-\log p(A|e, b, k)$ and $-\log p(k|e, b)$, the value is lower with the SBM-CC treatment for all networks considered. In other words, these figures show that SBM-CC is favored when $-\log p(A|B, e, k)$ and $-\log p(k|b, e)$ are considered, and SBM is favored for the two other components of the description length formula and the description length itself.

Furthermore, from Figure S5b, we can see that most of the ratio values concentrate close to 0. In other words, $-\log p(e)$ tends to have a higher increase with the CC treatment in comparison to $-\log p(b)$.

Explanation for a higher negative logarithm of the prior for the edge count matrix The formula for the negative logarithm of the prior for the edge count matrix is

$$-\log p(e) = \log \left(\frac{B(B+1)/2 + E - 1}{E} \right) \tag{3}$$

where B and E are the number of blocks and edges, respectively.

As B increases, this value will increase. Since the CC treatment will increase the number of blocks B by design, the negative logarithm of the prior for the edge count matrix will be higher.

(a) $DL(A, b)$

(b) $-\log p(e)$

(c) $-\log p(b)$

Figure S5: **SBM to SBM-CC ratios for the components of the description length where SBM is smaller.** Histogram of ratio of SBM for the description length (a) and two of its components (b, c) on the 103 networks that select the SBM(DC) model for community detection and clusterings obtained by both SBM(DC) and SBM(DC)-CC for each network. The ratios are $SBM(DC) / SBM(DC)-CC$. Note that the values are all between 0 and 1, indicating that SBM(DC) is the favored clustering with respect to the minimization of the description length and these components.

(a) $-\log p(A|b, e, k)$

(b) $-\log p(k|b, e)$

Figure S6: **SBM-CC to SBM ratios for the components of the description length where SBM-CC is smaller.** Histogram of ratios for two components of the description length on the 103 networks that select the SBM(DC) model for community detection and clusterings obtained by both SBM(DC) and SBM(DC)-CC for each network. The ratios are $\text{SBM(DC)-CC} / \text{SBM(DC)}$. Note that the values are between 0 and 1, indicating that SBM(DC)-CC is the favored clustering with respect to the minimization of these components.

E Commands and Versions

CC and WCC treatments on Leiden-`{mod, cpm}` were done with the Python code base. CC and WCC treatments on all models of SBM were done with the C++ code base. CC of both code bases are deterministic while WCC of each code bases may result in different outcomes each time depending on which mincut is selected when there is a tie. CM was only done through the Python code base.

SBM graph-tool can be found at <https://graph-tool.skewed.de/static/doc/> [1]. We used version 2.59 on Python 3.9.18.

```
1 import graph_tool.all as gt
2 g = gt.load_graph_from_csv(inputGraphName, csv_options = {'delimiter': '\t'})
3
4 clustering = gt.minimize_blockmodel_dl(g, state=gt.BlockState, state_args=dict(deg_corr=True
5 )) # for DC sbm
6 clustering = gt.minimize_blockmodel_dl(g, state=gt.BlockState, state_args=dict(deg_corr=
7 False)) # for Non DC sbm
8 clustering = gt.minimize_blockmodel_dl(g, state=gt.PPBlockState) # for PP sbm
9
10 description_length = clustering.entropy()
11 membershipFile = open(outputMemberName, "w+")
12 blockMembership = clustering.get_blocks()
13 for v in g.vertices():
14     nodeId = g.vp.name[v]
15     cur_block = blockMembership[v]
16     if cur_block < 0 or cur_block > num_nodes_total - 1:
17         continue
18     membershipFile.write((str)(nodeId) + "\t" + (str)(cur_block) + "\n")
19 membershipFile.close()
```

CC CC code can be found at <https://github.com/MinhyukPark/constrained-clustering>. The tag is v1.0.0.

```
1 ./constrained_clustering MincutOnly --edgelist <tab separated edgelist network> --existing-
2 clustering <input clustering> --num-processors <maximum allowed parallelism> --output-
3 file <output file path> --log-file <log file path> --log-level 1 --connectedness-
4 criterion 0
```

WCC WCC code can be found at <https://github.com/MinhyukPark/constrained-clustering> The tag is v1.0.0.

```
1 ./constrained_clustering MincutOnly --edgelist <tab separated edgelist network> --existing-
2 clustering <input clustering> --num-processors <maximum allowed parallelism> --output-
3 file <output file path> --log-file <log file path> --log-level 1 --connectedness-
4 criterion 1
```

CM CM code can be found at https://github.com/illinois-or-research-analytics/cm_pipeline The commit was alc1d29.

```
1 python3 -m hm01.cm -i <tab separated edgelist network> -e <input clustering> -o <output file
2 path> -c external -cfile <clusterer file path e.g., path to hm01/clusterers/
3 external_clusterers/sbm_wrapper.py> --threshold <threhsold e.g., 1log10> -cargs <
4 clusterer args path (json detail found in repository) > --nprocs <number of processors>
```

References

- [1] Peixoto, T.P.: The graph-tool python library. figshare (2014). DOI 10.6084/m9.figshare.1164194. URL http://figshare.com/articles/graph_tool/1164194